

YŷT:633.2.233

MEASURES TO INCREASE THE PRODUCTIVITY OF MOUNTAIN PASTURES.

¹Nazarov X.T., ²Xalilov X.T., ³Bobomurodova S.N., ⁴Boliyeva M.F.

1. Assistant Professor of Samarkand State University.

2. Researcher of Karakol and Desert Ecology Research

Institute

3. Student of Samarkand State University.

4. Student of Samarkand State University.

Annotation: The article discusses the issues of increasing the productivity and enrichment of plant biodiversity by phytomeliorating them with promising pasture forage plants to improve the condition of degraded natural pastures.

Keywords: Natural pasture, artificial pasture, pasture crisis, forage plants, phytomelioration, yield, efficiency.

Relevance of the topic. The main part of the areas used in livestock farming in our republic is considered natural springs and they are located mainly in arid region. The amount of annual precipitation in the arid region steppe, adir) is extremely low (160-250 mm) daily, seasonal, annual blisters of air temperature sharply variable blisters are crumbled, salted, as well as intensively suffocated to a different degree.

While natural springs are considered inexpensive, convenient and year-round fields that allow them to be used throughout the year, their nutrient reserves are extremely low (1,5-3,5 s/Ha), and vary dramatically throughout the Year seasons. Another case characteristic

of natural Sagittarius is that the saturation indicators of nutrients in them sharply decrease from spring to winter.

Also, as a result of non-compliance with the requirements of pastures (unsustainable use of shrubs and semi-shrubs for subsistence purposes, geological prospecting, use of mineral resources, overgrazing, etc.), high-nutrient species are gaining ground, pastures are in crisis. Improving the condition of natural pastures, their effective use, implementation of measures to increase productivity are among the most pressing agrobiological problems.

Research sources and methods. The source of the study is the light gray soils of the Nurata hills, ephemeral-ephemoid-type pastures, as well as semi-shrubs (sorrel, izen, terisken, tail) and perennial grasses astragalus, male grass). promising desert forage plants were selected.

Planned field experiments were carried out on the basis of biometric measurements to determine the yield of plants, the use of generally accepted methods in botany, agriculture.

Research results and their analysis. Studies have shown that Nutota foothills are more productive The productivity of natural pastures was determined by the "field" and "transect" methods. 'was measured on a weighing scale. Such samples were taken from 10 places of pasture to determine the yield, the average yield was determined and converted into hectares (s / ha). Transket - 4 corners are rectangular threads, secured with steel pegs and stretched when used, in our version they are 50 m long and 2 m wide. In this case, the number of semi-shrubs and large-stemmed species in the transket was determined, model species (large, medium, small) from each species were taken in 3 turns, weighed and weighed after drying. The average plant mass of each species was determined and the total weight of all species was added to the hectare, and the total yield was determined by adding the transitional species.

For research in the experimental field "Nurota" from drought-resistant high-yielding semi-shrubs (izen, teresken, chogan, tailed) and perennial grasses (astragalus, male grass) Artificial pastures were built from promising phytomeliorants, and their economic characteristics were studied and compared with natural pastures. It is known that the period

of highest yield and growth of pasture forage plants is the third year of their vegetation, and the growth, development and productivity of plants in subsequent years depend on weather conditions. The average yield may be more or less. Therefore, in the study, the yield of natural pastures was compared with the yield of artificial vegetation in the third year of vegetation in pastures.

Table 1.

Economic characteristics of pasture forage plants. Vegetation Vegetation 3 (2021).

Nurota Experimental Field

№	Types of plants	Number of plant balls in the viability photo thousand pieces / ha, in the denominator, %	Plant height, cm.	Pichan yield s / ha	Hay yield of natural springs to s/Ha
1	Izen	17,5±0,8	91,5±3,8	16,7±0,7	
		86,7			
2	Teresken	15,2±0,6	81,3± 3,6	14,9±0,5	
		78,3			
3	Chogon	14,3±0,7	84,7±4,0	15,3±0,6	
		75,6			
4	Weeds	14,8±0,5	72,4±3,1	13,7±0,4	
		72,8			
5	Astragalus	16,9±0,7	86,5±3,2	15,1±0,6	
		82,4			
6	Male grass	19,8±0,9	62,7±2,5	10,3±0,3	
		69,6			

Productivity (average)	14,3s/ga	2,8 s/ga
------------------------	----------	----------

The data from the table show that the survival (69.6-86.7%), growth (62.7-91.5 cm) and productivity (10.3-16) of pasture forage plants , 7) The productivity of artificially constructed pastures with a high level of performance averaged 14.3 quintals per hectare across plant species. This is 5 times more than the natural pasture yield (2.8 s / ha).

Phytomeleration of natural pastures by promising species of pasture-fed plants allows to achieve high efficiency. It is known that the annual feed requirement of one head of karakul sheep is 9 quintals of hay or 425 feed units. In 2021, the productivity of natural pastures of the Nurata hills will be 2.8 s / ha, which will require 3.2 hectares of pastures to feed one head of Karakol sheep. The yield of artificial pastures created from promising varieties of pasture forage crops is 14.3 quintals per hectare, which is enough to feed 0.63 hectares of pastures per head of karakul sheep.

At present, the price of 1 quintal of hay is 7,000 soums, and in 2021 the yield of natural pastures of the Nurata hills will be 2.8s / g and the income from it will be 196,000 soums. Yield of pastures is 14.3 s / g and the income from it is 1001000 soums. Expenditures on construction of artificial pastures (purchase of seeds, plowing, sowing of seeds) are made only once and these expenses The plants are covered in the second year of vegetation. In addition, artificial pastures have a consistently high yield for 25-30 years, and businesses are provided with guaranteed fodder.

Table 2

Cost-effectiveness of artificial pastures.

T/r	Indicators	Natural pasture	Artificial turf
1	Pasture area, ha	1	1
2	The yield of hay in the 3rd year of vegetation is s / ha	2,8	14,3
3	Pasture capacity for Karakol wells, head / ha	3,2	0,63
4	The total cost of the product is one thousand soums	196	1001
5	Pasture expenses, thousand soums		590
6	Net income from pastures, thousand soums		411
7	Profitability,%		69,6

Profitability net income = = 69.6%

Conclusions.

1. Determining the productivity of natural pastures is of medium importance in determining the process of their grazing and in determining the capacity of livestock for pastures.
2. Phytomelization of pastures with promising species of forage plants is a guaranteed measure that will allow to restore the vegetation cover of natural pastures, enrich their composition with new plant species with valuable nutritional properties and increase productivity.

List of used literature.

1. Maxmudov M.M., Sindarov J.Q., Xalilov X.T. Adir mintaqasi yaylovlari holatini yaxshilovchi istiqbolli fitomeliorantlar // Yaylovlardan oqilona foydalanish va muhofaza qilishning institutsionar masalalari. Toshkent. 2013. 275-279 b.
2. Xalilov X.T., Sindarov J.Q., Boboeyva A.S. Yaylov ozuqabop o'simliklari genofondidan tabiiy yaylovlar holatini yaxshilashda foydalanish //Oziq-ovqat xavsizligi : milliy va global omillar II-xalqoro ilmiy nazariy konferentsiya. Samarqand 2020. 546-548 b.
3. Q.S. Yarashev, Samyayev A.Q., Quyi Zarafshon tuproq qoplamining inson ta'sirida o'zgarishi //Quyi Amudaryo region ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy muamolarining geografik yechimlari. Respublik ilmiy –amaliy konferensiyasi materiallari. Urganch, 2010 – B. 165-168.
4. Q.S. Yarashev. Adir tog'oldi proyuvial tekislik mikroparagenitek landshaft kompleksi. // O'zbekiston geografiya jamiyati IX sezdi materiallari. –Toshkent, 2014.-B. 128-129. Q.S. Yarashev, Z. Nodirova . Zarafshon botig'ining tabiiy sharoiti va voha landshaftlari. //Ko'hna va novqiron geografiya. Toshkent, 2009. – B. 61-63
5. Q.S. Yarashev, Nazarov X.T., Xolmirzayev J.E.,Tog' yaylovlarini optimallashtirishning ayrim masalalari. //Qishloq xo'jaligiga innavatsion texnologiyalarni joriy qilish muammolari. Xalqaro konferensiya materiallari. T. 2. - Samarqand, 2012.